

SENSITIVITY THROUGH INVISIBLE WATER: MARRAKECH AS A MULTIFACETED CITY

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ABSTRACT

Marrakech is one of the four imperial cities of Morocco, declared as a UNESCO World Heritage site in 1985. The city centre was once surrounded by a vast palm grove which is called the Medina or the 'red city'. The urban area has been expanding beyond its Medina walls moving towards globalisation. This city is also famous for its rich water artefacts such as Water fountains, Khetaras, Riads, Hammams etc. which are among the main tourist attractions as well. With this strong character, set in the centre of the fertile, irrigated Haouz Plain, south of the Tensift River, the city is also called the 'Oasis city'. In recent years, with climate change, water scarcity and globalisation, the expansion of the city has left many multi-layered problems. One major issue is represented by the urban voids in between the city centre and the recent developments, acting as neglected spaces that together with water scarcity fades the character of the Oasis city and its heritage. Through an urban design exploration point of view, the research understands the city's main character of water, its accessibility, and its importance for the community. An investigation of the value and state of the water artefacts in the city using GIS data, existing literature, and possible approaches to bring back the Oasis City in the 'in between' urban voids of the city have been explored. The research aims to metaphorically evoke the idea of water in urban design to bring an intangible notion of water.

KEYWORDS

Water, Urban, Artefacts, Intangible

INTRODUCTION

Marrakech is the fourth largest city in Morocco. Located inland approximately 240km south of Casablanca, it was founded in 1062 by the Almoravids an imperial dynasty. Marrakech has a population by the year 2023 has reached approximately one million inhabitants. (Department, 2023). The city's economy relies mainly on tourism, handicraft production and commerce. The city of Marrakech is dependent on various natural resources for its development. One of the majors being water. Water as a resource is now scarce in the city (Aljazeera, 2018). To mitigate such risks, the Marrakech Local agenda 21 project was launched in 2002. (Habitat, 2021) Under this project an environmental profile was prepared. The key roles of the project focused on sustainable water management, improving the tourism and the urban and cultural heritage of the city. The project involved around 400 actors towards this vision. With such crucial roles of various actors and the scarcity of water, the research attempts to bring in the role of water in urban design for the city of Marrakech.

PURPOSE OF THE RESEARCH

The growth of the city has been fragmented leaving some vacant plots which become urban voids for the city. With a radial growth pattern, there is a change

in character observed from the cultural city also called as Medina to the suburbs Marrakech with visions towards globalisation. With this growth as mentioned earlier, water scarcity is a key concern in the city. Considering water as the theme of the research, the paper attempts to investigate the impacts due to water scarcity, the state of heritage water artefacts and their value in the current times. The paper aims to understand the notion of water in urban context and how the theme of water in a situation of scarcity can be used as metaphor in urban design.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The research investigates the issue of water in Marrakech through press review and virtual walk around the city. After these investigations various actors involved related to water are studied and an interrelation diagram with respect to the water elements is derived. After a general understanding of the context using the press review and understanding the various actors involved at local and global scale. The research maps the water elements such as drinking water fountains, Hammams, Riads, Khetaras etc which we call as the 'Water Artefacts' for Marrakech. The mapping is

carried out using QGIS software and the observations through the press review and virtual walk. These studies help to understand the role of heritage water artefacts and their current role in the water urbanism for Marrakech.

PRESS REVIEW

To understand the problems and the current crisis the city faces, a press review was carried out which showcases the issues related to water. Fig (1) shows the collection of data obtained through the press review. The press review was carried out to get a preliminary understanding of the city without getting into a detailed statistical review. This methodology aids to conceptualise the design ideas and problem setting during the conceptualisation of the design project. The press review highlights the steps taken by some actors towards developing sustainable strategies, the dilapidated state of water artefacts in the city, the reduced ground water table and strategies such as fog harvesting etc proposed in the city. The press review gives evidence of current situations the roles of various actors involved under the larger theme of water such as the Radeema, UNESCO, We Are Water Foundation etc. Apart from these formal actors, the press review highlights role of various private actors such as individual users in

the city which create a water competition in the city. The key issues seen through the press review are water scarcity, water competition, climate change and neglected water heritage. (Swiss, 2021). To understand the problems and the current crisis the city faces, a press review was carried out which showcases the issues related to water. Fig (1) shows the collection of data obtained through the press review. The press review was carried out to get a preliminary understanding of the city without getting into a detailed statistical review. This methodology aids to conceptualise the design ideas and problem setting during the conceptualisation of the design project. The press review highlights the steps taken by some actors towards developing sustainable strategies, the dilapidated state of water artefacts in the city, the reduced ground water table and strategies such as fog harvesting etc proposed in the city. The press review gives evidence of current situations the roles of various actors involved under the larger theme of water such as the Radeema, UNESCO, We Are Water Foundation etc. Apart from these formal actors, the press review highlights role of various private actors such as individual users in the city which create a water competition in the city. The key issues seen through the press review are water scarcity, water competition, climate change and neglected water heritage. (Swiss, 2021).

Marrakech solved the water riddle — through wastewater

STEPHANE DAKHAB & MELISSA NAUGHTON | MARCH 21, 2017
This page in English

Marrakech, Morocco, 1956: Situated 160 mi of Casablanca, and 100 miles inland on the foot of the Atlas Mountains, the Red City is being supplied for centuries with water through an intricate network of "shattaras" — man-made underground tunnels that captured runoff from the Atlas. The city is now developing and gaining an international reputation for its water demand starts to outgrow traditional re-utilities and farmers begin to tap into the local aquifer. By the 1970s, Marrakech soon relies exclusively on groundwater.

Morocco: Oasis on the front line of climate change

Al Jazeera's virtual reality documentary illustrates impacts of climate change on M'hamid oasis in Morocco's southeast.

UNICEF Morocco Hosts Meeting on Children's Rights and Water Scarcity

The meeting was held as part of the international "Reinventing the Future for Every Child" campaign.

Younis Bourjini June 17, 2021 3:28 pm

Morocco, between desertification and the pandemic

MOROCCO | MOROCCO WATER | MARRAKECH | COVID-19 | COMMUNITY | SUSTAINABILITY | EDUCATION

A new project of the Foundation promotes the access to water and hygiene in schools in Morocco's

The history behind the Fountains of Marrakesh

GARRETT CHRISTOPHER
After dates in Marrakech

Knowing how hot the weather can be in the red city, investing in refreshing fountains was a great idea. As of now there are around 90 fountains in Marrakech, and we are about to embark on the story of a

Makhal or Wind catchers and Salsabil or Courtyard fountain system: both wind catchers and courtyards in vernacular Arabic architecture use evaporative cooling to create a comfortable interior climate. The water element is usually a fountain or a small pool, that gets its water from a local source or man-made system of wells, called qanats.

A WALK THROUGH THE CITY

The research begun in September 2021 during the Covid -19 pandemic which limited the visit to the site and a virtual walk-through satellite images as well as through photographic data was carried out as an additional method to understand the city of Marrakech. The walk explored the various water artefacts in the city and their current state. The virtual walk helped to verify and understand in depth the issues that were highlighted through the press review as shown in figure 2. On one side of the city the heritage water artefacts such as the drinking fountains are not functional due to water scarcity, the other side private houses, resorts and hotels have large swimming pools. Marrakech is also known for its leather production; tanneries are important through an economical point of view to the city (Environmental Alternatives Unlimited, 2004).

Figure 1 Press articles related to water in Marrakech. Compiled by Authors

Figure 2 Observations during the virtual walk mapped by authors.

The process of making leather involves lot of usage of water and resulting in water pollution. This unequal distribution of water in the city has caused a social divide as well as a water competition in the city. Water competition is an issue directly linked with the local and governmental actors in the city. These observations from the press review and the virtual walk make it a mandatory step to understand the relation between the actors at various levels in the city.

WATER AND ACTORS

Figure 3 shows the various stakeholders, both at international level and governmental level and their relation to various intervention and strategies towards Urban design. The process of mapping the actors highlights the criticalities of maintaining transparency, coordination for the city. Marrakech is a cultural city with rich water heritage such as the Khettaras, Fountains, Hammams, Riads etc. These become the focus while mapping the actors related to water. The diagram also investigates the relation of the various local actors and users which get associated to the water artefacts. The diagram was developed in parallel to the literature and press study carried out for Marrakech.

THE WATER ARTEFACTS

Water fountains, Riads, Hammams and Khettaras are one of the most crucial water elements for the city of Marrakech, Apart from Khettaras they hold a social-cultural importance. Khettaras are traditional water systems for irrigation for agricultural lands. These water-related elements are a heritage for the city, and the authors call them 'Water Artefacts'. These artefacts become the guiding force for the urban analysis and design process Through the walk in the city and primary understanding of the city map, it can be concluded that the Water artefacts in the city are directly linked to the urban spaces and help in defining the character of the city. It can be said that through the study of water artefacts, the "DNA" of the city can be understood (Chataignier, 2017). The research maps the water artefacts in the city using various tools ranging from historic maps to satellite images and GIS data.

KHETTARAS

Khettaras are an ancient underground water systems used to carry water for irrigation of farmlands. (Stephane Dahan, 2017). Around hundreds of Khettaras have been registered in around Marrakech. The growth of the city has reached the

Figure 3 Relationship diagram of Actors, Source: - Authors

Figure 4 Khetaras and the river traced on historic maps. Source: - Authors

agricultural area, and an urban sprawl is observed. This urbanisation has led to over exploitation of the Khetaras through pumping of water as well as various bore wells have reduced the ground water table significantly. (Mohammed El Faiz, 2010). This urbanisation has left few Khetaras functional with limited stream of water while the rest are dry and redundant in the urban landscape. The study maps the Khetaras through the historic maps (Maps, 2020) and evidence through satellite imageries. Figure 4 shows and interpretation of the

Figure 5 Private water Artefacts Source: - Authors

layout of Khetaras and the river at a territorial scale around the city. The Khetaras are planned around the Medina gardens which helps in irrigation of the surrounding agricultural fields. The following analysis shows the course of the river and the overall layouts of the Khetaras through the historic maps. It is interesting to observe the how through time the Khetaras are now part of the larger city of Marrakech. The Southwestern part of the city has a dense network of Canals and Khetaras with water basin becoming the main spine for the irrigation

system. While Khettaras are more of a water irrigation system. The water artefacts such as fountains, hammams and riads are more related to the socio-cultural fabric of the city.

PRIVATE WATER ARTIFACTS

Artefacts such as Riads, Hammans have become the new tourist attractions. Most of them have been converted into heritage resorts or spas etc. They are associated to a commercial, hospitality or tourism business making them valuable though an economical point of view. Figure 5 shows the mapping of private gardens and pools which include some of the Riads and Hammans. Some artefacts especially located in the Medina (city centre) are accessible to public with entry tickets thus they have been categorised as semi-public.

PUBLIC AND SEMI-PUBLIC WATER ARTIFACTS

Figure 6 localises water related artefacts such as pools, fountains and hammams. Due to the water scarcity the water fountains have been closed by the municipality as a measure to save water. This has led to the water fountains as structure open to damage and misuse. This privatisation of few water artefacts while a few being in a dilapidated stage has left to a social void in the urban spaces of the city. The study of the public and private water artefacts helps to understand their interface with the urban spaces in the city and how it is crucial to revive them in order which can revitalise the urban spaces in the Medina (city centre).

Figure 6 Public and Semi-Public Water Artefacts Source: - Authors

Through this map we can see that most of the artefacts are concentrated in the Medina area and the distribution reduces as we move away from the city

Figure 7 Water Artefacts and the city Source: - Authors

centre. The Khettaras on the contrary are present outside the Medina wall for the agricultural fields.

DESIGN APPROACH Manifesto

Based on the design research carried out, a manifesto highlighting the urban conditions was developed. The process of developing the manifesto helps to define goals and future intentions for the design proposal. The manifesto helps in design research in three parts; the process of data collection in and knowledge, the curiosities towards the geography considered for design research and the directions to the designer for ideation in design processes. (Henry Mainsah, 2013).

The manifesto made after the study of the urban conditions of Marrakech showcases the gap between urban morphology between the medina and the new districts. The illustration summarises the study carried out. It highlights the gap in the socio economical structure of the city, where on one end there are large mansions with private pools and on the other side the dilapidated water artefacts in the Medina. This showcases the water competition and scarcity conceptually in the manifesto. The urban spaces lie in a neglected condition and the character of spaces linked to water heritage is absent in areas beyond Medina. The river being dry also becomes an urban void. The manifesto instigates a thought to question as how design interventions to answer the major concerns of water scarcity and competition can be dealt with. Water bodies and artefacts play a key role in activating the urban spaces. The heritage spaces act as an urban catalyst promoting various socio-cultural activities in the city.

SCALES OF COMPARISONS

Based on the manifesto and the research, an area of intervention between the Medina and Menara Garden was chosen for a design intervention. The reason for choosing this area was due to a need for better urban spaces and presence of prevalent Khettaras which brings in the connection of the theme of water for the design proposal. These in-between spaces hold a

Figure 8 Artwork Developed as a Manifesto. Source: - Authors

potential for bridge the gaps of the heritage city and transfer the cultural to the recent developing suburbs of the city. Figure 9 shows the development of the initial idea of the cultural axis, connecting Medina with the areas of intervention adjacent to Menara Gardens, exploring the relations within the urban fabric of the area and a possible first program proposal.

Figure 9 Cultural Axis. Source: - Authors

To understand the scale of the chosen area of intervention, a comparison of scale was done using public spaces known to the authors, this exercise helps the authors comprehend the site. Thus, the area of interventions was compared with Piazza Leonardo da Vinci, Milano, Duomo di Milano, and the city of Venezia as shown in figure 10.

Design Tool Kit Formulation

After the identification of overall problems, threats in the city and the area of intervention chosen, the

Figure 10 Scale of Comparison. Source:- Authors

idea of an oasis city manifested with a reminiscence to the water ponds present once in the area. Two Khettaras pass through the site now in dry state have also been considered to bring in the nostalgia of the traditional water system present in Marrakech. The design approach is to integrate these Khettaras in the form of public spaces. To develop an urban design proposal keeping water as a central theme and in a geography with water scarcity was the main challenge towards the design ideation. With the research carried out and the sensitivity developed towards the context, a concept of 'invisible water' emerged in the research process.

The figure 11 shows the mental mapping carried which helped in developing the concept of 'invisible water' and arriving to a design tool kit. The methodology of design thinking, and ideation helped in the developing the tool kit with various possible list of intervention that might be suitable for the city. The authors have developed a general tool kit, and all the elements in the kit need not suit the area of intervention. The tool kit has been developed as a general list for the Marrakech.

NARRATIVES FROM CASE-EXAMPLES

The research investigated design projects related to water as well as which have a poetic narrative. and sensitivity to water. Through the reading of the design philosophies of the various design projects, a qualitative aspect as well as a sensitive approach was developed for the design proposal for Marrakech. The case examples are as follows: -

Smitivan, Bhuj, India: The project is an earthquake memorial with a thought of a tree as a memory a victim who passed in the earthquake.

Figure 11 Arriving at the concept of 'invisible water'

The project uses water percolating reservoirs to increase the ground water table help in the growth of vegetation on a once barren mountain which is entirely the memorial site. The Smritivan Memorial is a project that has the power of making a new cultural landscape emerge from the ground (Fig. 4.14). With water reservoirs (Fig. 4.15) and different typologies of open-air public and gathering spaces (Fig. 4.16) the project connects the city with the new landscape and evokes the memory of the lost souls in the Bhuj earthquake. (VSC, 2018).

Ellora Caves, Aurangabad, India: - Ellora is a World Heritage Site located in India. Even if the terrain is different from that of Marrakech, the reference helped us to visualise the hierarchy of levels and their transitions. (Convention, 2018)

Hurva Synagogue, Jerusalem: - The unbuilt project by Louis Kahn for the historical Jerusalem's synagogue (Fig. 4.19) was an inspiration for us for

what concern) the use of massive walls for the definition of the interstitial space and the use of particular architectural prototypes as shading systems. (Margalith, 2018)

Lascaux Museum, France: - The French Museum welcomes visitors to an immersive educational experience of the prehistoric Lascaux cave paintings (Fig. 4.22). This case study helped us to imagine the articulation of the subterranean spaces and the entrance through gestures. (Archdaily, 2017)

Tunnel Borbonico, Naples, Italy: - The Borbonic Gallery, it's an underground cavity that spreads under the city of Naples. It is an example of the character that an underground built environment can produce, while emphasising on the historical water bodies. (Sotterranea, 2018)

DESIGN PROPOSAL

The design attempts to become a cultural axis to between the Medina and the Menara Garden.

Figure 12 Design Intervention. Source: - Authors.

With the character of Khettaras, a subterranean architecture has been conceptualised. The site will be excavated in some areas and the excavated soil will be used to manufacture brick that can be used as the building material. The design connects various markets and public spaces with the Khettaras at the underground level. The Khettaras once water system is visualised as connection and walkways for people to experience and celebrate the traditional water system. A crack has been proposed in the Menara Garden to symbolise water scarcity which connects the Khettaras. This crack represents water scarcity and invites the visitors to move into the Khettaras which have been converted into exhibits to celebrate the culture of Marrakech and create an awareness about the water artefacts. The design proposal ventures into a conceptual imagery to evoke the nostalgia of water without its presence. The design project suggests various interventions and recommendations to the area of intervention as shown in figure 12, 13, 14.

Figure 13 The crack with a subterranean urban project.
Source: - Authors

Figure 14 Khetgara Museum. Source: - Authors

CONCLUSION

The paper shows a methodology which can be helpful for design research and conceptual development of a project. The theme of water has been the primary object of the research, and it helped in developing a project that aims at enhancing water sensitivity without the use of water but it's through its preservation and metaphorical recalls. Marrakech is a multifaceted city with various plural identities with a strong involvement of local

and global actors. Understanding their role becomes a crucial factor as part of urban design research. The paper highlights how methods such as press review, design thinking can help in comprehending a geography efficiently.

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